

AG1. Interoperability & Standardization

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STOP-IT, iBathWater, SIM4NEXUS, F4W, NAIADES, SCOREWATER, Aqua3S, RESCUE, LOTUS, HYDROUSA, Smart Plant, NEXTGEN, RECONNECT, INNOQUA

Smart Water Data interoperability and standardization

“Curate, Reuse and Refurbish water data models”

Activities

- ✓ SAREF4WATR Setting up
- ✓ Harmonization of ontologies (SAREF) and reference architectures (FIWARE)
- ⚙️ Adoption of SAREF4WATR
- ⚙️ Data Harmonization across platforms
- ⚙️ Reaching semantic interoperability to water

Outcomes

- 📄 Guidelines and Methodologies to make data more interoperable
- 📄 Semantic Water Interoperability: A developer vision